

FAAM facility for airborne atmospheric measurements

FLIGHT FOLDER

Flight No.: B241
Date: 25th August 2006
Take Off: 13:54:38
Landing: 18:32:00
Flight Time: 4h37m22s

Campaign: DODO

Operating Area: Dakar to W

POB	Position	Name	Institute
1	Captain	Alan Foster	Directflight
2	Co-pilot	Steve Ball	FAAM
3	CCM	Gaynor Ottaway	Directflight
4	Mission Scientist	Ellie Highwood	Reading University
5	Flight Manager	Alan Woolley	FAAM
6	CCM2 / AVAPS	Doug Anderson	FAAM
7	SWS	Clare McConnell	Reading University
8	Cloud Physics	Martyn Pickering	Met Office
9	WAS / Core Chem	Jim McQuaid	Leeds University
10	Filters / PSAP	Paola Formenti	University of Paris 12 (LISA)
11	GRIMM	Gerard Capes	Manchester University
12	Mission 2	Hugh Coe	Manchester University
13	Mission Training	Mark Harrison	Met Office
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18			
19			
20			

Flight Track:

B241 Track 25-AUG-06

FLIGHT SUMMARY

Flight No b241
 Date: 25/8/08
 Project: DODO - DC8 Intercomparison
 Location: North of Dakar

Start Time	End Time	Event	Height (s)	Hdg	Comments
133833		engine start	0.22 kft	016	
133944		inu to nav	0.22 kft	016	
134242		power change	0.23 kft	016	
134304		push back	0.22 kft	016	+ taxi
135438		T/O	0.21 kft	353	
135438	140038	Profile 1	0.84 - 5.0 kft	329	
140748	141350	Profile 2	5.0 - 0.17 kft	327	
141350	143918	Profile 3	0.17 - 20.0 kft	316	
142431		Profile 3	10.0 kft	006	interrupt
142709		Profile 3	10.0 kft	159	resume
143218		Profile 3	15.0 kft	162	interrupt
143400		Profile 3	15.0 kft	013	resume
144418		ge max cool	18.0 kft	183	
145006		ge max cool	18.5 kft	358	stopped
145024		NASA DC8	18.6 kft	359	link up
145209		ge	19.0 kft	001	still dew layer
145540	150912	Profile 4	18.9 - 7.0 kft	000	
150912	152806	Run 1	7.0 - 7.1 kft	003	start at p4 end
151347		bbr	7.0 kft	004	shutter up (U)
152806	152931	Profile 5	7.1 - 8.0 kft	008	
152931		Run 2	8.0 kft	005	
154709	154924	Profile 6	8.0 - 7.0 kft	000	
154924	155124	Run 3	7.0 kft	003	
155142		NASA DC8	7.1 kft	327	break away
160537	162332	Profile 7	7.0 - 22.0 kft	210	
161252		Profile 7	14.0 kft	210	interrupt
161515		Profile 7	14.0 kft	065	resume
162437	162937	Run 4.1	22.0 kft	355	cross sun
163054	163728	Run 4.2	22.0 kft	267	up sun
163837	164404	Run 4.3	22.0 kft	179	cross sun
164514	165019	Run 4.4	22.0 kft	091	down sun
165648	165808	Orbit 1	22.1 - 22.0 kft	342	
165919	170040	Orbit 2	22.0 - 21.9 kft	041	
173233	175250	Profile 8	22.0 - 2.2 kft	166	
175250	181651	Run 5	2.2 - 2.0 kft	169	
175348		qnh 1013	2.0 kft	169	
183200		Land	0.22 kft	353	

B241 Track 25-AUG-06

FAAM Sortie Brief

*DODO2: in-situ sampling and radiometric measurements of mineral dust
Co-ordinated flight with the DC-8*

Flight No: B241

Date: 25 August 2006

Trial objectives:

To carry out in-situ sampling of mineral dust and measure the radiative effects over the ocean in conjunction with DC-8.

Location:

Over ocean areas off the coast of Senegal/Mauritania. Point alpha in North West quadrant.

Rendez-vous point – 16, 30N, 18, 30W

Point alpha – 20,30N, 18 W

Weather:

High loadings of dust. Cloudless skies preferred.

Special requirements:

Low-level (50ft) flying over ocean.

Formation flying!!!!!!

60 degree banked orbits at 1000ft.

2 dropsondes required.

Flight pattern:

1. Take off from Dakar at 14Z.
2. Ascend to 5000ft [5mins, T=5]
3. Once instrumentation is ready perform a profile descent to 50ft over ocean. [10min, T=15]
4. Profile ascent towards rendez-vous point at FL200 at 1000ft/min [20mins, T=35].
5. Profile descent to rendez-vous point at a level determined by our mission scientist and US LIDAR. [5mins, T=40]
6. Perform several in-situ sampling SLRs at different altitudes of 10 to 15 minute duration in conjunction with DC-8 in the direction of point alpha. Levels to be determined by our mission scientist and US LIDAR. Descents at 1000ft per minute [60mins, T=100].
7. Reciprocal turn.
8. If cloud free option of performing 60 degree banked clockwise orbits. Ascend to ~1000ft (above the sea-salt dominated layer) and perform four. [10min]
9. SLR at 100ft directly beneath the in-situ sampling runs towards original rendezvous point [30mins maximum, T=130].
10. Reciprocal turn. [5mins, T=135, ~100 minutes remaining.]
11. Perform two in-situ sampling SLRs at different altitudes each run of 10minute duration , or profile ascent to FL220 if no cirrus, to perform high level BBR/SHIMS/SWS calibrations.
12. Turn and SLR at FL200 (or above dust)
13. Profile descent to recover in Dakar [T=40mins, T=240mins].

Sortie Debrief B241 DC-8 intercomparison

Flight Number: B241

Date: 25th August 2006

Mission: Ellie Highwood

Sortie Objectives: Intercomparison with NASA DC-8. Formation in-situ sampling at levels determined by US Lidar, radiation work.

Operating area:

Originally along N-S line, 16N,1830W and 19N,1830W. Then in region near GUNET.

Weather: Extensive convective cloud between Dakar and around 19N. Relatively little dust in thin layers. Mostly to north of region.

Flight Patterns:

An early take off allowed plenty of time for an ascent to FL050 and then a descent to 50 ft over the ocean and a profile climb towards the rendezvous point at FL180, 16N:18,30W. This profile showed considerable convective cloud with StCu below between 1500 and 2500 ft. Another cloud level around 5000ft. Sea salt sampled (with blue neph reading high) in bottom 500ft of profile. Cloud top towards rendezvous point around FL150 although cirrus above. Dewpoints artificial at this point in the profile. After rendezvousing with the DC-8 we flew in formation and descended to FL070 which showed little dust. Nephelometer readings (submicron only) around 30Mm⁻¹, increasing slightly to the north. An in-situ run at FL070 was carried out, followed by an in-situ run at FL080. These runs took us substantially further north than the original plan so we broke from the formation at this point. Since the area was relatively cloud free, a broken profile ascent to FL220 was performed in the cloud free area followed by a box pattern with 5 minute legs, into, across, down and across sun. Two legs had SHIMS upper and two SHIMS lower. The SWS was ramped on the into sun leg, but visible module dropped out in down sun leg. One orbit at 57 degrees (7 over SZA) was performed before SWS dropped out again. A profile descent was completed to 2000ft towards the coast and Dakar (due to lack of fuel and dust and the presence of considerable cloud, no underflying of DC-8 line was completed.) Nouackchott was reporting blowing sand, but no outflow over ocean was observed. Multiple and thick cloud including CuNbs on way back.

Summary:

A successful in-situ intercomparison with the DC-8. Frustratingly little radiation work in conjunction with them due to cloud contamination on route. Also rather little dust, except possibly to the far north. Some radiometer calibrations completed.

Problems

SWS intermittent

Lower SHIMS has a shutter problem allowing only one module at a time.

Lower pyrgeometer still not working.

Neph needs calibrating? Blue scattering is very low all the time.

PSAP stopped logging for part of the run.

Flow rates may need re-calibration on neph and psap.

Frostpoint/dewpoint unreliable.

T/O 1354

4h30

1824

Aircraft Scientist's LogFlight No **B241**.. Date 25/8/06 Name ELLE HIGHWOOD.. Page 1.. of 2

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
Dakar					Humid! Cloud extensive but broken 8/4/8 bw 8/8 Mid
135438	P1	T/O → FLO50			Some whitecaps on sea Cloud base ~1500ft. top ~2500ft, Another level
140038	P1	FLO50	328		End profile in cloud Uniform neph @ 30m ⁻¹ up to FLO50 CO P slightly in bottom 500ft. Chem CAL
140748	P2 ↓	FLO50 ↓	327		1000ft/min
141148		1000ft 2000ft			500ft/min, sea state 1 - no white caps Blue neph has gone above red/green for first time in campaign!!
141350	P3 ↑				End ↓, start ↑ Cloud base 1000ft
142431	P3	FLO10			Profile interrupt. Extensive mid-level cloud
142709	P3 ↑	FLO10	161		Profile resumed
143218		FL150			P interrupt LIDAR 7000ft cloud top
	P3	FL200			End profile. Artificial Td currently.
144824					DC-8 sited
145540	P4 ↓	FL190 → 7000ft			1000ft/min Dust @ 9500ft
150942	P4	7000ft			End profile
150912	R1	7000ft			Run-neph 30m ⁻¹ Ci ↓ above towards North, neph picking up.

Aircraft Scientist's Log

24
18.30

Flight No **B241** Date 25/8/06 Name ELLIE HIGHWOOD Page 2 of 2

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
152931	R1 end R2 start	FL070↑			Ascending to ? FLO10
152936	R2	FL080			Interupt + profile, stat run.
	R2 end R3 start	FL070			
	R3 start	FL070			
155124	R3				End 15724 run Break formation
160547	P10	FL220			
161252		FL140			P interupt
161515					P resume
1623		FL220			End profile
162440	R4.1				end 162937 cross sun
163054 163228	4.2				Into sun
163837 164404	4.3				Cross sun.
164514	4.4				Down sun lost SWS
165648	O1				Stat 57° 40 ° SWS back SZA 51.9
165808	O1				End
165919	O2				Stat 57° 40 ° SWS out east way through
170040	O2				end
173233	P11	FL220↓	169		Profile down towards coast
					Nauackhoff reporting blowing sand. Multiple cloud layers on way down
					CuNs to east, storms reported
					Dakar.
					Cloud @ FLO10
175201	P11	2000ft			
	R5				Stat recovery run to Dakar

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG Flight B241

Date: 25/10/06	Operator: MAP	DRS Time: 12:00:00	DAU1 Time:	DAU2 Time: + 3	DAU3 Time: +0	Aux1 Time: +0	Aux2 Time: +0	Page 1 of 1
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G.M.T	PCASP		FFSSP	SID1	SID2	2D2-C		2D2-P		CIP25			CIP100			Habit	Remarks
	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block TX	Count	Count	Conc/L	Max size	Conc/m3	Max size	Conc m3	Max size	LWC	Conc m3	Max size	LWC		
13:54:38																Start Profile 1 from Take off	
13:57:01	380	0.09		70												FL020	
13:58:20	300	0.09		70												FL030	
13:59:51	220	0.09		80												FL040	
14:00:35	180	0.09		1000		35	400	400	800						1	End of Profile 1 @ FL050	
14:07:45	170	0.10		20												Start Profile 2 from FL050	
14:08:55	400	0.09		150												FL040	
14:09:51	400	0.10		100												FL030	
14:10:46	600	0.09		90												FL020	
14:11:49	700	0.09		100												FL010	
14:13:45	700	0.09		90												End of Profile 2 & start Profile 3 @ 50'	
14:15:56	550	0.09		100												FL010	
14:16:59	400	0.09		100												FL020	
14:17:59	200	0.10		20												FL030	
14:18:55	180	0.10		20												FL040	
14:19:55	125	0.10		20												FL050 Heaters on	
14:20:50	100	0.11		20												FL060	
14:21:46	50*	0.11		10												FL070	
14:22:28	20*	0.11		10												FL080	
14:23:30	10*	0.11		5												FL090	
14:24:29	15	0.11		5												FL100	
14:28:12	10*	0.10		5												FL110	
14:29:20	5*	0.09		2												FL120	
14:30:19	5*	0.09		2												FL130	
14:31:14	5*	0.09														FL140	
14:32:08	5*	0.09														FL150	
14:35:00	5*	0.09														FL160	
14:36:10	5*	0.09														FL170	
14:37:20	5*	0.09														FL180	
14:38:29	5*	0.09														FL190	
14:38:20	5*	0.09		2												End of Profile 2 @ FL200	
14:55:45	5*	0.06														Start Profile 3 from FL190	
14:56:58	5*	0.08														FL180	
14:57:59	5*	0.07														FL170	
14:59:01	5*	0.07		1												FL160	
15:00:04	5*	0.09														FL150	
15:01:03	5*	0.09		2												FL140	
15:02:00	5*	0.09														FL130	
15:03:00	5*	0.07														FL120	
15:04:04	5*	0.07		5												FL110	
15:05:00	5*	0.08		5												FL100	
15:06:01	10*	0.06		5												FL090	
15:07:04	30*	0.08		10												FL080	
15:09:09	50*	0.08		10												End of Profile & Start Run 1 @ FL070	
15:10:00	50*	0.08		10													
15:12:00	70	0.11		10													

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG Flight B241

Date: 25/10/06	Operator: MAP	DRS Time: 12:00:00	DAU1 Time:	DAU2 Time: + 3	DAU3 Time: +0	Aux1 Time: +0	Aux2 Time: +0	Page 2 of 2
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G.M.T	PCASP		FFSSP	SID1	SID2	2D2-C		2D2-P		CIP25			CIP100			Habit	Remarks
	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block TX	Count	Count	Conc/L	Max size	Conc/m3	Max size	Conc m3	Max size	LWC	Conc m3	Max size	LWC		
15:14:00	70	0.10		10													
15:16:00	70*	0.13		10													
15:18:00	70	0.10		10													
15:20:00	80	0.10		15													
15:22:00	70	0.11		15													
15:24:00	70	0.12		15													
15:26:00	40	0.12		10													
15:28:06																End of Run 1 & Start Profile 5	
15:29:21	50	0.12		20												End of Run 5 & Start Run 2 @ FL080	
15:30:00	90	0.12		30													
15:32:00	90	0.12		30													
15:34:00	90	0.12		30													
15:36:00	100	0.12		40													
15:38:00	80	0.12		30													
15:40:00	75	0.11		20													
15:42:00	65	0.11		10													
15:44:00	65	0.11		10													
15:46:00	80	0.10		10													
15:47:00																End of Run 2 & Start Profile 6 from FL080	
15:49:21																End of Profile 6 & Start Run 3 @ FL070	
15:50:00	100	0.11		20													
15:52:00	100	0.10		10													
15:54:00	100	0.10		10													
15:56:00	90	0.10		10													
15:58:00	80	0.10		15													
16:00:00	75	0.11		15												End of Run 3	
16:05:31	105	0.13		60												Start Profile 7 from FL070	
16:06:30	70	0.12		20												FL080	
16:07:47	60	0.10		10												FL090	
16:08:46	45	0.11		10												FL100	
16:09:49	35	0.12		10												FL110	
16:10:48	20	0.08		5												FL120	
16:11:40	20	0.08		5												FL130	
16:12:40	20	0.08		5												FL140	
16:16:23	20*	0.08		2												FL150	
16:17:22	20*	0.08		1												FL160	
16:18:35	20*	0.08														FL170	
16:19:30	5*	0.08		1												FL180	
16:20:31	5*	0.08		1												FL190	
16:21:29	5*	0.06		1												FL200	
16:22:30	5*	0.06														FL210	
16:23:29	5*	0.06		1												End of Profile 7 @ FL070	
16:24:37																Start Run 4.1 @ FL220	
16:25:00	5*	0.06		1													
16:27:00	5*	0.06															
16:29:00	5*	0.06															

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG Flight B241

Date: 25/10/06	Operator: MAP	DRS Time: 12:00:00	DAU1 Time:	DAU2 Time: + 3	DAU3 Time: +0	Aux1 Time: +0	Aux2 Time: +0	Page 3 of 3
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G.M.T	PCASP		FFSSP	SID1	SID2	2D2-C		2D2-P		CIP25			CIP100			Habit	Remarks
	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block TX	Count	Count	Conc/L	Max size	Conc/m3	Max size	Conc m3	Max size	LWC	Conc m3	Max size	LWC		
16:29:35																End of Run 4.1	
16:30:52																Start Run 4.2 @ FL220	
16:31:00	5*	0.06															
16:33:00	5*	0.06															
16:35:00	5*	0.06															
16:37:00	5*	0.06															
16:37:34																End of Run 4.2	
16:38:34																Start of Run 4.3 @ FL240	
16:39:00	5*	0.06															
16:41:00	5*	0.06															
16:43:00	5*	0.06															
16:44:01																End of Run 4.3	
16:45:13																Start Run 4.4 @ FL240	
16:46:00	5*	0.06															
16:48:00	5*	0.06															
16:50:20																End of Run 4.4	
16:56:42																Start Orbits	
17:00:37																End of Orbits	
17:32:32	5*	0.06		1												Start Profile 8 from FL220	
17:36:47	5*	0.06		1												FL180	
17:41:06	5*	0.06		1												FL140	
17:44:44	5*	0.06		1												FL100	
17:45:57	25*	0.15		2000		1000	100								1	FL090	
17:47:03	50*	0.14		3000		1500	200								1	FL080	
17:48:11	70*	0.08		3000		300	350								1	FL070	
17:49:11	80	0.08		200		80	400								1	FL060	
17:52:55																End of Profile 8 & Start Run 5 @ FL020	
17:53:00	160	0.08		?												SID1 screen closed for landing	
17:55:00	80	0.08		?													
17:57:00	300	0.09		?													
17:59:00	270	0.09		?													
18:01:00	250	0.09		?													
18:05:00	280	0.09		?													
18:10:00	300	0.09		?													
18:15:00	330	0.09		?												Heaters Off	
18:16:51																End of Run 5	
	*Estimates when the PCASP noisy in Channel 1 & channel 7																
	Flowrate = 1.35 CC/sec																
	2D2-P switched off at high altitude return transit to reduce file size due to noise																
	FFSSP & SID2 not fitted																
	CIP100 not operated																

SWS FLIGHT LOG SHEET

Flight #	B241	Date	25/8/06	Operator(s)	C. McCONNELL	log page	1	of	2
Time	Run id	Alt/FL	Mirr Pos	Int Times		Remarks			
				Vis	NIR				

SWS

134244	grnd		GF	15	15	Dark			
134301						Rec			
140606						Dark			
140617						Rec			
145242				50	30	Dark			
14656						Rec			
141923						Dark			
142106				75	15	Dark			
142233 ¹⁷						Rec - no VIS.			
142423				100	30	Dark			
142435						Rec - NO VIS			
142739				100	30	Dark			
142750						Rec - no VIS			
143622				100	30	Dark			
143636						Rec			
143717				50	15	Dark			
143727						Rec			
145257			174H	50	15	Dark			
145325						Rec - NADIR			
145364	145540	PL4				Dark			
151632				100	30	Dark			
151710						Rec			
151754				200	75	Dark			
151806	R1			200	75	Rec			
153557						Dark			
153611				250	100	Rec			
153719						Dark			
155228				350	200	Dark			
155242						Rec			
160230				350	400	Dark			
160242						Rec			
161418			GF	350	400	Dark			
161437			GF	350	400	Rec - shutter closed			
161452						Rec			
162227						Dark - sample = 0.1sec			
162247						Rec - " "			
162437	R4-1					Cross sun			
162801				350	500	Dark			
162815						Rec			
163057	R4-2		37F			Rec - into sun			
163139	R4-2		25F			Rec			
163228	R4-2		15F			Rec			

SWS FLIGHT LOG SHEET

Flight # **B241** Date **25/8/06** Operator(s) **C MCCONNELL** log page **2** of **2**

Time	Run id	Alt/FL	Mirr Pos	Int Times		Remarks
				Vis	NIR	

SWS

163307	R4.2		6F	350	500	Rec
163348	R4.2		4A			Rec
163428	R4.2		15A			Rec
163506	R4.2		25A			Rec
163546	R4.2		35A			Rec
163619	R4.2		45A			Rec
163653	R4.2		55A			Rec
163732						Dark
163744			66F			Rec - shutter closed
163754	R4.3					Rec - open, on ^{cross} sun
164517	R4.4		55A			Rec - Down sun
164555	R4.4		35A			Rec
164636	R4.4		25A			Rec
164723	R4.4		15A			Rec - VIS signal lost
164815	R4.4		5A			Rec
164857	R4.4		6F			Rec
164934	R4.4		15F			Rec
165032			6F	200	350	Dark - samp = 0.55
165136						Dark
165208						Dark
165219						Rec
165359			6F	200	350	Dark
165314						Dark
165423						Rec
165549						Dark
165558	01					Rec - sample period = 0.1 sec visax
165847			6F	75	150	Dark
165854	02					Rec - VIS lost.
170124						Dark
170160						
170203				150	150	Dark
170213						Rec
170400				100	150	Dark
170409						Rec
170969				200	250	Dark
171014						Rec
173836						Dark
173846	D11					Rec
183431						Dark

SHIMS

SWS FLIGHT LOG SHEET							
Flight #	B241	Date	25/8/06	Operator(s)	C. MCCONNELL	log page	1 of 2
Time	Run id	Alt/FL	Mirr Pos	Int Times		Remarks	
				Vis	NIR		

SHIMS

	USH					
1405						Time set
140518				50	100	Dark
140535						Rec - USH
140704						Dark
140813				50	100	Dark
140852						Rec
140942				100	200	Dark
140954						Rec
141123						Dark
141313				100	200	Dark
141321	P2					Rec
144856						Dark
144905						Rec
145204						Dark
	LSH					
145458				100	200	Dark
145508						Rec
150509				200	200	Dark - false
150526				200	200	Dark - OK
150541						Rec
151223						Dark
151242						Rec
151439						Rec - no signal
151432				200	200	Dark
151450	R1					Rec
152342						Dark
152458				200	200	Dark
152513						Rec
153335						Dark
153516				200	200	Dark
153530						Rec
154319						Dark
154533				250	250	Dark
154351						Rec
161650						Dark
161843				250	250	Dark
161852						Rec
162439	R4.1					cross sun - LSH, ^{also} into sun
163909						Dark
163901	USH			10	200	Dark - USH
163911	R4.3			10	200	Rec - cross sun

Flight Manager's Instrument Status Log

Flight No. **B240**

Date: 24 August 06

Instrument	Fitted	Operated	Instrument	Fitted	Operated
<u>Navigation</u>			<u>Cloud Physics</u>		
INU	Y	Y	<u>Probes</u>		
XR5M GPS	Y	y	FFSSP	Y	N
Cruciform GPS	Y	Y	PCASP	Y	Y
Satcom C	Y	Y	2D-P	Y	Y
Satcom H	Y	Y	2D-C	Y	Y
<u>Thermometers</u>			Cloudscope	N	
De-Iced Temp	Y	Y	SID 1	Y	Y
Non De-Iced	Y	Y	SID 2	N	
Heimann	Y	Y	HVPS	N	
<u>Hygrometers</u>			CIP25	N	
G. Eastern	Y	Y	CIP100	N	
J. Williams	Y	Y			
Nevzorov	Y	Y			
TWC	N				
FWVS	N		<u>Racks:</u>		
<u>Radiometers</u>			INC	N	
Upper Clear	Y	Y	CCN / CNC	N	
“ Red	Y	Y	CVI	N	
“ IR	Y	Y			
“ SHIMS	y	Y	<u>Aerosol</u>		
Lower Clear	Y	Y	PSAP	Y	Y
“ Red	Y	Y	Nephelometer	Y	Y
“ IR	Y	Y	Filters	Y	Y
“ SHIMS	Y	Y	AMS	Y	N
<u>Large Radiometers</u>					
TAFTS	N				
MARSS	N				
DEIMOS	N		<u>Others:</u>		
ARIES	N		NIR TDLAS	Y	N
SWS	Y	Y	2BT O3	N	
<u>Chemistry</u>			VACC	N	
Ozone	Y	Y	PEROXIDE	N	
SO2	Y	N	Formaldehyde	N	
NOX	Y	Y	ADA	N	
CO	Y	Y	CPI	N	
ORAC	N		NOxy	N	
PAN	Y	Y	PTRMS	N	
PERCA	N		Bag Sampling	N	
WAS	Y	Y	Tube Sampling	N	

Faults / Incidents Log

Flight No. B241

Date: 25 August 2006

Instruments

Muck in Ffc requires window to be removed
Lower bbr(ir) u/s and no spare.

Aircraft

Satcom H Calls

MISSING LOG SHEETS:

The following log sheets are not available for flight B241:

Log	Reason
Cloud Physics Processing	Awaiting processing completion
AVAPS	No sondes were dropped on this flight.
PSAP	No log appears to have been taken for this flight
Filters	Awaiting completed log
Core Chemistry	no In Flight log except in cases of instrument problems
GRIMM	No log currently available
WAS	No log currently available

VIDEO RECORDINGS:

2 x Upward Facing Cameras
2 x Rearward Facing Cameras

Digital8 video recordings from this flight reside with :

Dr. Eleanor J. Highwood

Senior Lecturer in Climate Physics
Department of Meteorology
University of Reading
Reading
RG6 6BB

Tel: +44 (0) 118 378 6688
Fax: +44 (0) 118 378 8905

E-mail: e.j.highwood@reading.ac.uk